

Cyano-complexes of Bivalent Rhenium

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In reporting preparation and properties of several cyano-complexes of bivalent rhenium^{1,2}, Sen observed that these compounds could be oxidised by suitable oxidising agents like bromine, acidic hydrogen peroxide, and acidic permanganate to the corresponding complexes of trivalent rhenium. The present authors have determined the formal potentials of the systems: $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} / [\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$ and $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{3-} / [\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$ and their variation with pH. The remarkable similarity in the properties of the cyano-complexes of iron(II) and rhenium(II), qualitatively observed by Sen, has been quantitatively investigated by us.

As the cyano-complexes of trivalent rhenium are rather unstable and it is difficult to isolate them in the pure state, the solutions of sodium aquo-pentacyanorhenate (II) and sodium hexacyanorhenate(II) of known concentration have been titrated with standard oxidants, like ceric sulphate, potassium permanganate, etc., at different pH's. The formal potential values and the number of electron changes have been determined from a plot of observed E.M.F. against $\log [\text{oxidant}] / [\text{reductant}]$. Fig. 1 shows the variation of formal potentials of these systems with pH.

FIG. 1. Formal potential as a function of pH.

I: System $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} / [\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$.

II: $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{3-} / [\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{2-}$.

III: $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-} / [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$.

1. Sen, *Science & Culture*, 1958, 23, 664.

2. *Idem*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1952, 315, 315.

3. Charlot, "Theory and New Methods of Qualitative Analysis", 3rd ed., 1949, p. 300.

4. Davidson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 50, 2622.

The apparent normal potentials of the different systems are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Systems.	Apparent normal potentials (volt).	Temp.	Ref. No.
$[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$	-0.72 at $p\text{H}=0$	25°	3
$[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}/[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}$	-0.72 at $p\text{H}=0$	30°	..
$[\text{Fe} \begin{smallmatrix} \text{H}_2\text{O} \\ \text{(CN)}_5 \end{smallmatrix}]^{3-}/[\text{Fe} \begin{smallmatrix} \text{H}_2\text{O} \\ \text{(CN)}_5 \end{smallmatrix}]^{2-}$	-0.489 in <i>N</i> -KCl	21°	4
$[\text{Re} \begin{smallmatrix} \text{H}_2\text{O} \\ \text{(CN)}_5 \end{smallmatrix}]^{3-}/[\text{Re} \begin{smallmatrix} \text{H}_2\text{O} \\ \text{(CN)}_5 \end{smallmatrix}]^{2-}$	-0.636 at $p\text{H}=0$	30°	..

The redox system

is a reversible one and the colour of the oxidised form is intense green. Possibility of the utilisation of this system as a redox indicator in various titrations is being explored. The details of the work will be published later.

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